

OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION – A PROMISING TOOL TO ENHANCE PRODUCTIVITY: A CASE OF R V INSTITUTE OF MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Outcome Based Education (OBE) has become a buzzword in the education space and more so ever in the higher education space. Most of the accreditations - be it national or international, including NAAC and NBA today gives a lot of importance on the OBE. Strong emphasis is laid on the ability of the Institution to follow the principles of OBE to the core and not for the name sake. This is where decoding the entire process of OBE as conceptualized in the Bloom's Taxonomy becomes relevant and important to enhance productivity of all the processes including Teaching - Learning - Evaluation. In this paper, which is conceptual in nature, an attempt has been made to understand the processes involved in OBE as substantiated with a real world case of a standalone B-school of eminence of India, i.e. R V Institute of Management, Bangalore.

KEYWORDS: *Outcome Based Education, R V Institute of Management, Accreditation, Higher Education & Bloom's Taxonomy*

INTRODUCTION

The central philosophy around which the Outcome Based Education practice revolves is Bloom's Taxonomy. Bloom's taxonomy is a guide for strengthening the Teaching-Learning-Evaluation processes in the context of higher education institutions, irrespective of the courses offered. The three important domains VIZ Cognitive domain (Knowledge domain: Knowing – Head), Psychomotor domain (Skills domain: Doing – Hands) and the Affective domain (Attitude domain: Feeling – Heart) highlighted in the Bloom's taxonomy¹ and the positioning of the course with regard to different levels in each domain needs to be looked into while framing and delivering the curriculum for a specific course. This is where understanding the different levels in each domain becomes very critical in enhancing the productivity of all the processes including teaching-learning-evaluation. In the following section, different levels in each domain will be presented in a pictorial way in order to gain a broader understanding of the Learning that happens at the higher education as learning per se doesn't only mean ability to remember and reproduce knowledge.

Cognitive Domain (Knowledge Domain): Knowing –Head

Figure 1

Psychomotor Domain (Skills Domain): Doing - Hands

Figure 2

Affective Domain (Attitude Domain): Feeling - Heart

Figure 3

Application of the Bloom's Taxonomy to the Teaching-Learning-Evaluation Process

Following picture very clearly explains the relationship of Bloom's taxonomy with the OBE.

Figure 4

As presented in the picture above, OBE (Outcome based Education) drives the entire teaching-learning-evaluation process in a higher education space. Thus knowing the process involved in OBE becomes very essential. Broadly the process involves nine stages as depicted in the picture presented below;

- Setting Graduate Attributes (GAs)
- Setting Program Educational Objectives (PEOs)
- Setting Program Outcomes (POs)
- Setting Course Outcomes for each course (COs)(within a program)
- Setting Module wise outcomes for each module (MOs)(within a course)
- Mapping the Course Outcomes with the Program Outcomes
- Checking the Attainment level of the Course Outcomes, Program Outcomes and also the Program Educational Objectives
- Taking measures to increase the attainment levels
- Revisiting GAs, PEOs, POs, COs, MOs at regular time intervals as they are dynamic in nature and change according to the context.

Figure 5

Case of R V Institute of Management²

Attempt has been made in this section to apply the above process for a higher education institution in framing the GAs, PEOs, POs for an MBA program and also the COs and MOs for the Entrepreneurship Development course.

Graduate Attributes

Table 1

RVIM's Graduate Attributes	
Attributes	Descriptor
Subject Knowledge proficiency and Application	Graduates will demonstrate comprehensive knowledge in their functional domains and apply it to professional practice
Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship	Graduates will show entrepreneurial orientation by demonstrating creativity and Innovation in professional and personal situations
Communication, Presentation and Negotiation skills	Graduates will convey ideas and information effectively to the stake holders involved and be able to negotiate
Data Analysis, problem solving and Decision making	Graduates will apply logical, critical and creative thinking to solve a range of problems for data-based decision making
Global Orientation and Cultural Sensitization	Graduates will be able to understand and appreciate people from different cultures and nationalities. Operate effectively in cross-cultural settings, understanding the nature of globalization
People Management, Leadership and Team Orientation	Graduates will Lead themselves and others in the achievement of organizational goals, contributing effectively to a team environment
Research Aptitude, Critical Thinking and Cognitive Flexibility	Graduates will be able to think critically with cognitive flexibility and develop an aptitude towards research
Self Awareness, Self Reflection and Life long learning	Graduates will understand their own self and their reflections on others and engage in lifelong learning
Social Responsibility, Ethical Behavior, Inclusive Growth and Sustainable Development	Graduates will adapt to a rapidly changing environment through learning and applying newer skills and become socially responsible and ethically driven citizens committed to inclusive growth and sustainable development
IT Skills & Business Analytics	Graduates will be able to use contemporary information technology tools and techniques independently to enhance

Program Educational Objectives²

PEO 1: Graduates will be able to demonstrate effective decision making, cognitive flexibility, problem solving capability and adapt to the changing global environment

PEO 2: Graduates will be capable of innovating, starting new entrepreneurial ventures and be each a lifelong learner with multidisciplinary research aptitude

PEO 3: Graduates will be able to think critically; communicate effectively; demonstrate analytical skills, team spirit, and leadership qualities

PEO 4: Graduates will be able to demonstrate professional values, cultural sensitization, ethical behavior and integrity

PEO 5: Graduates will be as responsible global citizens and contribute towards inclusive growth and sustainable development of the society

Program Outcomes²

PO1: Apply knowledge of management theories and practices to solve business problems

PO2: Foster Analytical and critical thinking abilities for data-based decision making

PO3: Ability to develop Value based Leadership

PO4: Ability to understand, analyze and communicate global, economic, societal, cultural, legal and ethical aspects of business

PO5: Ability to lead themselves and others in the achievement of organizational goals, contributing effectively to a team environment

PO6: Ability to identify business opportunities, frame innovative solutions and launch new business ventures or be an intrapreneur

PO7: Ability to deal with contemporary issues using multi-disciplinary approach with the help of advanced Management and IT tools and techniques

PO8: Ability to apply domain specific knowledge and skills to build competencies in their respective functional area

PO9: Ability to engage in research and development work with cognitive flexibility to create new knowledge and be a lifelong learner

PO10: Ability to understand social responsibility and contribute to the community for inclusive growth and sustainable development of society through ethical behavior

PO11: Ability to function effectively as individuals and in teams through effective communication and Negotiation skills

Course Outcomes (CO) and Module Wise Outcomes (MO) for a Sample Course: Entrepreneurship Development³

CO 1: Understand the nuances of entrepreneurship

CO 2: Understand the dynamics for startups and success of new ventures.

CO 3: Critically analyze, how the fundamental concepts and tools may be applied to real world business situations and opportunities

CO 4: Gain an understanding of how entrepreneurial thought and action may be applied to opportunities of all kinds including new ventures as well as innovation within existing organizations, in both for profit and not for profit sectors.

CO 5: Use a methodology to develop and assess new opportunities to convert an idea into reality and to be able to create B Plans in addition to the ability of raising funds.

CO 6: Inculcate the ethical framework of leadership as an entrepreneur.

Module Wise Outcomes for each of the Modules of Entrepreneurship Development Course

- **MODULE 1: ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE NEW MILLENIUM**

MO 1: Understand who can be termed as an Entrepreneur in the present world.

MO 2: Understand the contribution of entrepreneurship towards economic development of India

- **MODULE 2: OPPORTUNITY ASSESSMENT**

MO 3: Understand the process of identifying an opportunity converting it into an idea and implementing the idea.

MO 4: Verify the uses and abuses of various sources of funds available for startups.

- **MODULE 3: FEASIBILITY ANALYSIS AND CRAFTING BUSINESS PLAN**

MO 5: Conduct Feasibility Analysis for (Industry, Market, Product or Service)

MO 6: Develop and Create a Business Plan and create a business model.

- **MODULE 4: LEGAL FORMS OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ORGANIZATIONS**

MO 7: Analyze the various Legal Structures and Forms of Business Ownership

MO 8: Evaluate the Business Environment

- **MODULE 5: SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP**

MO 9: Understand why social entrepreneurship is different from the other forms of entrepreneurship

MO 10: Realize the need for more social enterprises

- **MODULE 6: ETHICS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP**

MO 11: Understand what is an Ethical Dilemma

MO 12: Realize the importance of ethics in business

CONCLUSIONS

Even though the OBE process appears to be simple and straight forward, lot of thinking, discussion and

deliberations need to happen at each and every stage as it is directly linked to the accomplishment of mission and vision of the Institution. OBE is simply a tool to enhance productivity of the Teaching – Learning – Evaluation processes aimed at realizing the mission and vision of the Institution. Choosing the right action verbs (words) while framing the GAs, PEOs, POs, COs and MOs is very crucial and important as each action verb (word) reflects unique level in the order of the learning in each of the three domains as narrated in the earlier section. Some of the action verbs for different levels of learning in the Cognitivedomain are illustrated here-in-under⁴;

Table 2

Bloom’s Taxonomy Action Verbs

Definitions	Knowledge	Comprehension	Application	Analysis	Synthesis	Evaluation
Bloom’s Definition	Remember previously learned information.	Demonstrate an understanding of the facts.	Apply knowledge to actual situations.	Break down objects or ideas into simpler parts and find evidence to support generalizations.	Compile component ideas into a new whole or propose alternative solutions.	Make and defend judgments based on internal evidence or external criteria.
Verbs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arrange • Define • Describe • Duplicate • Identify • Label • List • Match • Memorize • Name • Order • Outline • Recognize • Relate • Recall • Repeat • Reproduce • Select • State 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classify • Convert • Defend • Describe • Discuss • Distinguish • Estimate • Explain • Express • Extend • Generalized • Give example(s) • Identify • Indicate • Infer • Locate • Paraphrase • Predict • Recognize • Rewrite • Review • Select • Summarize • Translate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply • Change • Choose • Compute • Demonstrate • Discover • Dramatize • Employ • Illustrate • Interpret • Manipulate • Modify • Operate • Practice • Predict • Prepare • Produce • Relate • Schedule • Show • Sketch • Solve • Use • Write 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyze • Appraise • Breakdown • Calculate • Categorize • Compare • Contrast • Criticize • Diagram • Differentiate • Discriminate • Distinguish • Examine • Experiment • Identify • Illustrate • Infer • Model • Outline • Point out • Question • Relate • Select • Separate • Subdivide • Test 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arrange • Assemble • Categorize • Collect • Combine • Comply • Compose • Construct • Create • Design • Develop • Devise • Explain • Formulate • Generate • Plan • Prepare • Rearrange • Reconstruct • Relate • Reorganize • Revise • Rewrite • Set up • Summarize • Synthesize • Tell • Write 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appraise • Argue • Assess • Attach • Choose • Compare • Conclude • Contrast • Defend • Describe • Discriminate • Estimate • Evaluate • Explain • Judge • Justify • Interpret • Relate • Predict • Rate • Select • Summarize • Support • Value

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